

Constraints to the use of molecular assisted selection in the genetic improvement of indigenous livestock in Nigeria: a review

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Abstract

Indigenous livestock production is intertwined with the life style of Nigerians. The Nigerian livestock industry employs the bulk of the rural work-force. These breeds are distributed across the diverse agro-ecological production systems, and are carriers of unique and responsive genotypes shaped by the needs of their managers. Despite their unique features, most indigenous livestock breeds are characteristically low in production and productivity. Improvement of these breeds represents a logical starting point for improving food security and agricultural productivity in Nigeria. To better understand natural genetic variation in these indigenous livestock breeds and strategies for improvement, better genetic characterization is required. Molecular assisted selection (MAS) will be valuable in the pursuit of selection for increased production, but the application of MAS to livestock improvement is constrained by a variety of limitations. The focus of this paper is to elucidate the potential of MAS as a tool for genetic improvement of indigenous livestock, to identify constraints and challenges in MAS implementation and propose solutions to increasing MAS feasibility in pursuit of improved food security and sustainability in Nigeria.

Key words: Food security, Genetic improvement, Genomic Selection, Indigenous livestock, Marker assisted selection, Nigeria

Introduction

In Nigeria, livestock plays an important role in the national economy, accounting for as much as one third of the country's agricultural gross domestic product (GDP) (1). Nigeria is home to a diversity of indigenous livestock breeds (2),(3)

Despite their beneficial features, most of these indigenous breeds are characteristically low in productivity.

Past efforts geared at improvement have been based on upgrading of available indigenous breeds with imported exotic breeds or complete replacement of indigenous stocks with such imported improved breeds. However, most imported improved exotic breeds from Europe and North America failed to perform true to their genetic potential, when raised in Nigeria (2) or some other tropical environments in Africa (4), different from the sanitized environments and temperate climates for which they were originally developed.

MAS is yet to reach its full potential for livestock improvement in developing countries, like Nigeria, where investments have been much more limited (4).

Nigeria is endowed with a rich diversity of livestock species, majority of these species have received little to no attention or investment in

genetic improvement or conservation programs. Proper molecular characterization and MAS utilization will be valuable to increasing indigenous livestock productivity. This paper will elucidate a number of constraints to successful MAS implementation for genetic improvement of indigenous livestock in the drive for improved food security and sustainability. Literature materials on livestock improvement, conservation and Marker Assisted Selection were assembled and collated from Journals, Conference Proceedings, books and from the internet, they were then reviewed and discussed

Current limitations to the Application of MAS Genetic structure and compelling environmental pressures

The large number of different livestock breeds and varieties in an array of production indicates that animal diversity has developed over time and in response to the ecosystem (5). Nigeria is particularly well endowed with livestock diversity, and most breeds have been reared under low-input, extensive systems with very little reproductive control. Uncontrolled mating on pasture or free ranging is the common practice, much in contrast to the highly structured breeding programs and

intensive selection used in the developed world.

In the rare cases where selection is controlled, the resulting livestock are product of a few key selection criteria. Their parents were picked for their resilience to harsh environments, disease resistance or reproductive potential. Limiting breed selection to only a few traits risks erosion of genetic diversity (6) so special effort must be taken to conserve diversity through breeding for a variety of traits.

High Cost of implementing MAS for livestock improvement

Application of molecular techniques in enhancing improved livestock production can be expensive. In the words of (7), “economics is the key determinant for the application of molecular genetics in genetic improvement programs.” The cost of importing tools and equipment from developed countries can be so high that the benefit derived is insufficient (8). Current development in next generation sequencing (NGS) techniques, offer cheaper alternatives that make MAS research more achievable. Furthermore, investment in training of trainers who in turn can develop increase workers’ skills and knowledge through local training organizations will go a long way to improve MAS technology implementation.

Poor Research and Development (R and D) policy and priorities

In developed countries, most of the plant and animal breed improvements achieved with MAS can be credited to local non-governmental institutions and collaborative ventures between the public and private sectors (9). These types of collaboration are largely absent in Nigeria, and much of the developing world. Encouragement of open market policies that allow public-private partnership in organized MAS application to indigenous animals and plant germplasm, could go a long way to drive genetic improvement and development of highly productive novel breeds.

Poor Funding for R and D

Research involving molecular technologies is often thwarted in Nigeria due to inability of researchers to access grants and funds (8). Attracting quality investors to Nigeria for MAS technology-based R and D, has proven to be very challenging because most institutions could not provide the basic equipment/facilities required to effectively carry out basic MAS related research. The issue is further exacerbated by the dearth of local grant awarding institutions. The few available ones have their priorities directed away from long term agricultural projects.

Instability of Electricity

In Nigeria, electricity supply is very erratic and research is often forcefully terminated as a result of irregular power supply (8). Some experts have argued that this erratic power supply appears to be the most challenging factor impeding human activities in developing countries (10, 11, 12, 13). More so, Nigeria, like most African countries, has great potential for solar energy. If this natural energy source is harnessed as a result of investment in solar energy alternatives, this could ease some of the problems with erratic power supply.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Molecular assisted selection is a cost-effective and promising technique for driving genetic improvement in the livestock industry not only in Nigeria, but all over the developing countries of the world. Support for public and private investment in molecular technology can improve agricultural production, productivity and sustainable growth in the livestock sector in pursuit of food security. Government should provide more funds for research and development especially in the area of animal genetic improvement.

Government’s increased role in establishing a positive enabling environment for research, implementing policies for livestock breed improvement programs, and funding indigenous livestock conservation efforts will go a long way in promoting improved livestock productivity and can make real contributions to food security and economic growth in Nigeria

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